

PrehistOman Project, Season 2024

Report of Seasonal Activity

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Introduction

During the last decades, research on Omani Prehistory of the Holocene period has primarily focused on the coastal fringes (Cleuziou & Tosi 2018). The excavation of significant shell-middens has provided valuable insights into the lifestyle and transformations of hunter-fisher-gatherer communities, suggesting that from the end of the 6th millennium cal BCE, human communities settled along the coastal areas and intensively exploited resources from both open-sea and inshore waters. Sites like Ra's al-Hamra (RH6 and RH5) (Muscat), Wadi Shab (GAS-1) (Tiwi), Khor Mhilk I and II (Quriyat), Ra's al-Khabbah 1 (KHB-1), Suwayh (SWY-1), Ruways 1 (RWY-1) (Ja'lan region), with their thick stratigraphic sequences and rich material records, have provided substantial evidence to reconstruct the main aspects of their lifestyle, including dwelling types, subsistence activities, and symbolic and burial practices (Charpentier 2008; Méry and Charpentier 2013; Beuzen-Waller et al. 2019).

Decades of archaeological excavations at Ra's al-Hamra (RH6 and RH5), for example, have revealed evidence of various types of huts and shelters, typically oval or C-shaped, constructed directly on the bedrock. These huts were built using organic materials such as wood and reeds, with structural elements supported by post-holes reinforced with wedging stones. The presence of multiple hearths, pits, and processing areas within these settlements indicates a well-organized use of space for daily activities. The material record includes a broad and diverse array of tools and artifacts, suggesting that specialized craftsmanship activities were carried out within the sites. Notably, the site yielded mother-of-pearl fishhooks and beads made from various shell species, reflecting the importance of marine resources not only for subsistence but also for producing personal adornments and possibly for long-distance interactions. Additionally, the presence of graves within the shell midden, including several with grave goods such as shell bracelets and stone tools, suggests that these communities had developed complex social and ritual practices (Biagi et al. 1989; Marcucci et al. 2014, 2021).

The settlement patterns of these communities are still under debate, particularly regarding their level of sedentarization (Biagi & Nisbet 2006). Most authors argue that the abundance of marine resources may have encouraged permanent settlements with year-round occupations. The exploitation of the ecological niches—particularly coastal open water, reefs, estuaries, and mangroves—supplied the necessary food sources. Pelagic species were supplemented by catching demersal fish, small fish, and molluscs from the cliffs, estuaries, or mangroves (Marrast et al. 2023). The discovery of large cemeteries at some sites, such as those at Ra's al-Hamra, also suggests a certain degree of social complexity and possibly a more settled lifestyle than previously assumed. Recent isotopic studies from RH-5 strongly support this hypothesis, suggesting low mobility (or only mobility along the coast) for the individuals living on the coastal fringe (Zazzo et al. 2014). In this context, nomadic migrations between the coastal and highland zones were likely limited due to a strong preference for coastal and mangrove environments. Expeditions to the mountains would have been undertaken primarily in the summer heat, when temperatures were more moderate, and water-rich highland plains were available (Biagi & Nisbet 2006).

Despite these recent advances, the degree of mobility patterns and territorial organization of the human communities that inhabited northeastern Oman during the Middle Holocene remains an open question. Our interpretative framework is strongly biased by the fact that data about the occupation of inland areas is much scarcer and more discontinuous compared to the coastal fringe. The number of surveyed sites in inner regions is limited, and there are fewer sites with stratigraphic deposits. Most information about these areas comes from surface findings, thus lacking clear chronological attribution and contextual information. Nevertheless, the recent discovery of inland Neolithic sites such as Jebel Al-Aluya (Lemée et al. 2013), Al-Buhais 18 (Uerpmann et al. 2020), Wadi al-Hilo 1 (Uerpmann et al. 2018), Qumayrah sites (Białowarczuk & Sczymczak 2020), and Hayl Ajah 1 (Mateiciucová et al. 2023) opens new possibilities for enhancing our understanding of the South Arabian Neolithic.

The current joint project, *PrehistOman “Excavations and survey at Hayy al-Sarh-Rustaq (Al Batinah South Governorate, Oman)”*, undertaken by the University of Pisa and the Sultan Qaboos University,

aims at investigating one of those sites, recently discovered, located in inner areas of northwestern Oman, Hayy Al-Sarh site. The site of Hayy Al-Sarh has been identified as part of a larger survey program in the Al Batinah governorate undertaken by [Kennet et al. \(2016\)](#). On the basis of preliminary research, it seems that Hayy Al-Sarh is one of the few sites in the foothill area of Al Batinah South that preserves a stratigraphic deposit with a rich lithic assemblage dated to the Neolithic period. Initial fieldworks at Hayy Al-Sarh were conducted by [Bretzke et al. \(2018\)](#) and [Bretzke & Parton \(2020\)](#). Their work involved surface collections of lithics and the excavation of four small test trenches, three of which were 1x1 meters in size and one measuring 4x2 meters. These test trenches identified two main archaeological layers (AH-I and AH-II) containing flaked stone tools and malacofauna. Radiocarbon dating of two marine shells confirmed that the site dates to approximately between 5500-5400 cal BCE and 4900-4800 cal BCE, aligning with the Neolithic period, as suggested by the presence of bifacially retouched points in the flaked stone tool assemblage.

During the 2023 campaign, organized in the framework of the Al-Tikha Omani-Italian joint project directed by Prof. Khaled A. Douglas (Sultan Qaboos University - SQU) and Prof. Sara Pizzimenti (University of Pisa - UniPi), a first survey in the area was conducted by N. Mazzucco and his collaborators, focusing on the evidence of pre-Neolithic and Neolithic occupations in the Al Batinah South governorate ([Figure 1](#)). As results of this survey campaign, new data was gathered on the occupation of foothills and the mountainous areas of the Central Al-Hajar. Two new lithic scatter areas with prehistoric materials were identified, and a new scatter was identified in the Hayy Al-Sarh area. In addition, outcrops of radiolarite potentially exploited by prehistoric groups were identified in the Rustaq area.

Figure 1 Above: points of interest (N=103) recorded during the 2023's survey (Bing Virtual Earth, QGIS v. 3.26.3), with indication of Hayy Al-Sarh site (blue star); Below: Satellite photo of Hayy al-Sarh site with the indications of the previously surveyed area (in green) during the 2023 campaign.

Methods and aims of 2024 excavation campaign

The 2024's campaign was intended to set up an extended excavation in the Hayy Al-Sarh site, opening an area of about 20x10 meters. This expansion was aimed to:

- test the stratigraphic sequence identified by [Bretzke et al. \(2018\)](#).
- enable a better understanding of the site's spatial organization.
- the exploration of possible domestic structures or dwellings.
- collect of a larger sample of materials from stratified layers.
- collect samples for paleoenvironmental analysis.
- collect new samples for radiocarbon dating.

The methodology of excavation was based on the double strategy, including the realisation of small surveys (TEST) to delimitate the extension of the archaeological layers and understand the geomorphological setting of the site, and the opening of larger trenches (A1 and A2) to put into light the presence of possible anthropic features ([Figure 2](#)).

- The absolute coordinates of all archaeological materials recovered in position and of all structures were recorded using a Trimble C5 Total station. Orthophotos and 3D models were generated using photogrammetry with Agisoft Metashape, all integrated into a QGIS environment.
- Sediments were sieved using both dry-and wet-sieving. For superficial and sterile layers ¼ of the total sediments was dry sieved (i.e., SUP, US3000,), while for layers containing archaeological materials (i.e., US3001; US3002; US3003) the entire volume was sieved. Samples were taken from relevant structures for wet sieving using 0.05 mm and 0.1 mm sieves.
- All materials and samples recovered from excavation were recorded into an Excel inventory separated for category of remains (Flaked Stone Assemblage – LTA; Macrolithic elements – LIT; ORN – Ornaments; MCO – Malacological remains; SED – Sediment samples).

The 2024's team was composed by 13 members, of which nine participated at on field activities, while the other specialists worked in laboratory on materials and samples.

Type	Name	Role	Affiliation
Researchers	Prof. Niccolò Mazzucco	Direction	Dep. Civiltà e Forme del Sapere, Università di Pisa (Italy)
	Prof. Khaled A. Douglas		College of Arts & Social Sciences, Sultan Qaboos University (Oman)
	Prof. Nasser Al-Jahwari		
	Dr. Luca Biancalani	Excavation and topography	Professional Archaeologist (Italy)
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Trainees	Alvise Bianchi	Excavation and topography	Dep. Civiltà e Forme del Sapere, Università di Pisa (Italy)
	Claudia Finocchiaro		
	Giada Pirrone		
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Figure 2 Above: view of the stratigraphic test by Bretzke and colleagues; Below: Indication of the main excavation area (A1, A2) and some of the tests realized.

Results

Main Excavation Area

Cleaning of the Main Excavation Area

The first activity was the surface cleaning of the Main Excavation Area. A 20 x 10 meters area was defined on the right bank of the hill, near an outcrop of ophiolite bedrock. Cleaning was made by brushing all superficial sediments and sieving them on a 5 mm sieve. No archaeological materials were present in the superficial sediments.

A1 Trench

A 5 x 5 meters trench (A1) was opened at the western side of an outcrop of ophiolite bedrock. The original idea was to test whether the Neolithic inhabitants installed their occupation near the rock. The first stratigraphic test realized by Bretzke and colleagues was indeed located on the eastern side of the ophiolite bedrock.

Six main US were identified, almost all of them sterile of archaeological materials (Figure 3). A main difference was noted in the sedimentological composition of the layers. On the east side of the A1 Trench, we observed a fluvio-colluvial deposit made by medium and small rounded pebbles, while on the West side the deposit was composed of a weekly bedded sandy layer. This suggests that the original geomorphological setting of the Pleistocene terrace (US1005) changed since the Neolithic period, with the natural slope gradually filled by sandy sediment derived both from water stream and aeolian action (US1001-US1002-US1004). The only archaeological remains of the entire trench, a flint flake, was found in US1004, in the eastern sector of the excavation, might suggesting that an archaeological layer was still preserved in the lower, western, sector of the slope.

US	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	Volume(L)	Findings	Explanation
1000	sand	rocks, gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	n/a	None	Eolic sediment of sandy matrix with gravel and rocks. Archaeologically sterile.
1001	sand	rocks, gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	700	None	Eolic sediment of sandy matrix with gravel. Archaeologically sterile.
1002	sand	n/a	Loose	Homogeneous	sandy	1000	None	Fluvial deposit made of pure sand. Archaeologically sterile.
1003	sand	gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	reddish-brown	500	None	Altered deposit of reddish-brown colour of geological nature. Archaeologically sterile.
1004	sand	gravel	Compact	Homogeneous	sandy	300	Flint (scarce)	Weekly bedded sandy layer. Possibly archaeological.
1005	pebbles	sand, small gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish, sandy	2500	None	Fluvial-colluvial deposit of the Pleistocene terrace. Archaeologically sterile.

Table 1. List of US of A1 Trench

Figure 3 General view of A1 Trench with the schematic representation of the South Section.

A2 Trench

To test for the presence of an archaeological layer equivalent to US1004 on the western side of the slope, we opened a new trench measuring 6 x 4 meters (24 m²) on the west side of the hill. This new area, designated as AREA A2, revealed archaeological materials, including flaked flint tools, from the superficial layers. The first layer encountered, US3001, is an aeolian deposit of loose, fine sands, homogeneously distributed across AREA A2, and it covers the underlying archaeological layer. Beneath this, we uncovered a more compact layer, US3002, which likely represents the abandonment phase of the occupational layer and serves as its covering. US3002 is characterized by a fill of calcareous stones and small to medium-sized gravel. The main archaeological layer is represented by US3003. As we progressed through these stratigraphic units, the number of lithic remains gradually increased: 39 in US3001, 165 in US3002, and 392 in US3003. To further investigate the depth and extent of the archaeological layers, we conducted a test pit (TEST PIT 5) that provided a complete stratigraphic sequence (Figure 6). Below US3003, we identified two geological layers. US3100 is a layer of sand with occasional small to medium-sized rocks and contains few archaeological materials, likely percolated from the overlying layers. The bottom layer, US3101, is a weakly bedded sandy deposit, probably formed by slow-moving or stagnant water. This suggests that there is only one archaeological horizon present, with no additional underlying archaeological layers uncovered. Within US3003 several features have been defined: LOCUS1, and LOCUS2, and a series of smaller structures, among which US3009 and US3016.

Figure 4. Excavation process of LOCUS1, through the main US, US3001, US3002, US3003.

LOCUS1. This feature starts to be visible from US3001, gradually appearing clearer through US3002 and US3003 (Figure 4). It is a U-shaped stone structure, featuring an opening to the northeast. The enclosing wall consists of two rows of larger stones measuring 30 x 40 cm, filled in with smaller stones. The structural stones rest directly on the floor, and no foundation trench was observed. Some gaps or empty spaces were noted in the external stone border. The interior of the structure is relatively clear, with only a few knapped flints discovered, while numerous artifacts are found in the exterior. The LOCUS1 remains of uncertain interpretation; it maybe represents a dismantled dwelling. Features of similar shape have been found in other inland Neolithic contexts. This is for example the case of LOCUS 8001 from Jabal al-'Aluya (Lemée et al. 2013), or some surface structures as found at QA 41 in the Qumayrah Valley (Białowarczuk 2020). However, LOCUS1 but may also serve as a form of terracing to level the slope and separate the occupational area from the exterior.

Locus	US	Type	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	L	Explanation
1	3004	layer	sand	rocks of medium dimensions	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	60	Sediment surrounded by aligned stone, probably linked to an occupation.
1	3017	structure	stones	rocks of large and medium dimensions	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	Rather chaotic alignment of huge stones of U-shaped form.

Table 2. List of US of A2 Trench, LOCUS1

Figure 5 Above: orthophoto of US3003 and related features. Below: Schematic representation of A2, with the main occupational layer, US3003, LOCUS1, LOCUS2, and US3009 and US3016.

LOCUS2. During the excavation of US3003, a possible posthole (US3005) with a greyish-coloured fill was discovered on the eastern edge of the excavation area. This finding prompted us to enlarge the excavation area by an additional 16 m², bringing the total excavation area to approximately 40 m² (Figure 5). As a result, a new and complex set of structures, designated as LOCUS2, was uncovered. LOCUS2 features an arched outline, defined by a compacted alignment of small to medium-sized stones (US3010). Along its border, a series of pseudo-circular postholes, associated with round or roundish stone circles, was identified. These postholes and possible postholes (US3005, US3008, US3007, US3012) are relatively small, with diameters ranging from 25 to 40 centimetres (Figure 8). The internal space of this structure, designated as US3017, contained a significant quantity of flaked stone remains—about a hundred—as well as a shell bead and a coral fossil. To date, only half of this roundish structure has been excavated, with the remaining half scheduled for excavation during the next campaign. While the interpretation of the structure remains open, we currently hypothesize that it may represent the remains of a circular dwelling. A shelter with a similar outline was recently excavated by Białowarczuk and Sczymczak (2019) in the Qumayrah region.

Locus	US	Type	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	L	Explanation
2	3005	structure	sand	ashes	Loose	Homogeneous	greyish	5	Negative feature of elliptical shape, 37x26 cm, 7 cm deep. After a first layer of ashy sand the bottom of the pit was filled with small stones. Probably a posthole.
2	3007	structure	sand	stones	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	5	Pseudo circular shallow pit of undefined limits. Maybe a posthole.
2	3008	structure	sand	gravel	Loose	Heterogeneous	greyish	5	Pseudo circular shallow pit of undefined limits. Dimensions are 21x26 cm, 5 cm deep. Maybe a posthole.
2	3010	structure	stones	sand	Loose	Homogeneous	greyish	n/a	Alignment of medium-sized stones, it could be interpreted the limit of the hut structure
2	3011	structure	sand	stones	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	3	Pseudo circular alignment of stones.
2	3012	structure	sand	stones	Loose	Homogeneous	greyish	4	Pseudo circular shallow pit. Dimensions are 20x23 cm, 6 cm deep. Maybe a posthole.
2	3013	structure	sand	stones	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	5	Pseudo circular alignment of stones.
2	3014	structure	sand	stones	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	3	Pseudo circular alignment of stones.
2	3015	structure	sand	stones	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	4	Pseudo circular alignment of stones.
2	3017	layer	sand	medium gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	100	Internal space of the possible hut.

Table 3. List of US of A2 Trench, LOCUS2

Figure 6. Schematic representation of the eastern section of A2. This section has been made in correspondance of a Test Pit 5 in order to test the potency of the archaeological sequence in area A2.

US3009 and US3016. North of LOCUS2, a shallow circular pit, approximately 20x20 centimetres in size and 5 centimetres deep, was uncovered. The fill consisted primarily of charcoal mixed with ashy sandy sediment, making it the only structure where charcoal was clearly recognizable macroscopically. Its interpretation remains ambiguous; while the abundant charcoal suggests a possible connection to a combustion process, the pit's small dimensions raise questions about its exact function. Samples for C14 dating, whose analysis is currently ongoing, have been taken. On its western margin, a pseudo-circular alignment of stones (US3016) was identified, raising the possibility of an association between post holes or pits and these circular stone agglomerations (Figure 7). These two structural types may be connected, as observed in LOCUS2. It is possible that US3009 and US3016 are also part of LOCUS2, but for now, we prefer to keep these two entities distinct.

US3006. US3006 has been identified as the continuation of US3003, extending west of LOCUS1. In the western sector of the excavation (Figure 5), in the southwestern corner, there is an accumulation of large stones, approximately 40 cm in diameter, which appears to be a natural deposit along the slope. Overall, there is a relatively small quantity of archaeological materials in this area, suggesting that it may be outside the main occupational floor.

Locus	US	Type	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	L	Explanation
n/a	3001	layer	sand	rocks	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	1160	Aeolian deposit of fine sand which covers the archaeological layer.
n/a	3002	layer	sand	rocks, calcareous gravel of small and medium size	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	1350	Geological layer with a sandy matrix of aeolian origin. Filled with rocks and small and medium sized gravel. Covers the archaeological layer, therefore contains a relevant amount of flaked stone tools.
n/a	3003	layer	sand	mostly rocks, gravel of medium and large sizes	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	560	Archaeological layer with a rather flat occupational layer with medium sized stones and archaeological materials in flat position
n/a	3006	layer	sand	big stones, rocks, medium and large gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	370	The layer contains big stones of 40 cm of diameter, mostly located in the southern corner. There is a minor quantity of archaeological materials, which allows to think to be right outside of the occupational floor.
n/a	3009	structure	ashy sands	charcoals, gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	black, greyish, brown	3	Circular pit of 20x20 cm, 5 cm deep. The external perimeter presents few stone on the northern side. It was filled with dark ashes and small chunks of charcoals; it could be interpreted as a hearth.
n/a	3016	structure	sand	stones	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	1	Pseudo circular alignment of stones near US3009. Uncertain interpretation.
n/a	3100	layer	sand	small gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	n/a	Identified only in TEST PIT 5. A layer of sand with occasional small to medium-sized rocks, containing few archaeological materials likely percolated from the overlying archaeological layers.
n/a	3101	layer	sand	n/a	Compact	Homogeneous	yellowish	n/a	Identified only in TEST PIT 5. This layer likely represents a weakly bedded sandy deposit, probably formed by slow-moving or stagnant water.

Table 4. List of all other US from A2.

Figure 7 Left: zenithal view of US3009 at its discovery. Right: View of US3009 and US3016 at the end of the excavation process.

Figure 8 View of LOCUS2 with some of the main features identified.

Other Test Pits

A series of test pits have been realised also outside of the main excavation area to better define the extension of the archaeological layer and to gather data on the geomorphological setting of the area (Figure 2).

Test Pit 1. The first test pit, measuring 1 x 1 meter, was excavated near the test trenches conducted by Bretzke et al. (2018) (Figure 2). The primary goal was to gain a better understanding of the stratigraphical dynamics on the eastern side of the slope. Beneath a sterile layer (US2001) approximately 20 cm thick, we identified a relatively flat and thin archaeological layer (5 cm thick) with an abundant flaked stone assemblage, designated as US2002. This layer likely corresponds to the layer AH-I identified by Bretzke and colleagues and appears to be the easternmost continuation of US3003. Below US2002, we encountered US2003, a more heterogeneous and compact sandy sediment. A few archaeological materials were found in this layer, but they are interpreted as contaminants from the upper layer. Finally, a geological layer (US2004) dominated by fine gravel was detected, most likely representing the base of the Pleistocene terrace. Unlike the findings of Bretzke et al. (2018), we did not identify any additional archaeological layer (AH-II) at the bottom of the test pit.

US	Type	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	Thickness	Explanation
2001	layer	sand	small stones and pebbles	Compact	Homogeneous	dark yellowish, brownish, greyish	20 cm	Aeolian and colluvial deposit of fine sand. The upper part is laminated.
2002	layer	fine sand	few small, fragmented rocks and rocks	Loose	Heterogenous	yellow	5 cm	Layer rich in archaeological material. Some of the larger pieces are retrieved in a flat position.
2003	layer	sand	few stones	Compact	Heterogenous	brownish	15 cm	Sandy layer with few archaeological materials, maybe contaminated from the upper one.
2004	layer	gravel	sand and small and medium sized stones	Loose	Heterogenous	brownish	n/a	Geological layer composed by a loose gravel and small and medium-sized stones

Table 5. List of US from Test Pit 1

Test Pit 4. A second test pit, also measuring 1 x 1 meter, was excavated in the flatter area at the base of the hill (Figure 2). Based on data gathered from trenches A1 and A2, this sector was hypothesized to be an area of possible water circulation and sediment accumulation. As expected, no archaeological layers were found, and the test pit proved to be sterile. Beneath a superficial layer of predominantly aeolian sands (US4001), we unearthed a thick, bedded sandy layer (also designated as US4001), which had accumulated on top of the Pleistocene terrace (US4002) (Figure 9). This confirmed our hypothesis that this area was subject to sediment accumulation from slow-moving water activity.

US	Type	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	Thickness	Explanation
4001	layer	sand	few stones	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	15 cm	Aeolian deposit of fine, loose, sand.
4002	layer	sand	sand	Compact	Homogeneous	yellowish	35 cm	Homogeneous layer of pure sand, likely a deposit of fluvial origin.
4003	layer	sand	few small, fragmented rocks	Loose	Heterogenous	yellowish, brownish	20 cm	Geological layer composed of loose sand with abundant rounded rocks, likely part of a Pleistocene terrace.

Table 6. List of US from Test Pit 4

Figure 9 View of TEST PIT 4, location, and North Section.

Test Pit 7. A further test pit, measuring 1 x 1 meter, was excavated at the northern extremity of the terrace to investigate the presence of an archaeological layer in this sector, at about 50 meters from the main excavation area (Figure 2). Like previous tests, an initial sterile aeolian deposit was encountered, followed by the presence of an archaeological layer containing a scatter of flaked stone materials. The test pit was not fully excavated, as the primary objective was mainly to test the spatial extension of the archaeological materials.

US	Type	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	Thickness	Explanation
7000	layer	sand	stones, gravel	Loose	Heterogeneous	brown, dark grey	20	Geological layer made of big and medium sized rocks.
7001	layer	sand	rare gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	50	Aeolian deposit of sand with rare presence of gravel.
7002	layer	sand	small and medium sized rocks	Loose	Heterogeneous	yellowish	80	Archaeological layer defined by the presence of flaked stone tools and medium sized rocks.
7003	layer	sand	gravel	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	30	Archaeological layer with flaked stone tools. It has been only partially excavated.

Table 7. List of US from Test Pit 7

Test Pit 8. As for test pit 7, to document the distribution of archaeological materials in the area, a stratigraphical survey has been made in further south-east, at about 50 meters of distance from the main excavation area (Figure 2). Also in this case, an archaeological layer with a relatively dense lithic scatter was found.

US	Type	Fill	Other fills	Texture	Uniformity	Colours	Thickness	Explanation
8000	layer	sand	big pebbles	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	n/a	Geological layer with aeolian sediment.
8001	layer	sand	big pebbles	Loose	Homogeneous	yellowish	n/a	Geological layer made of sand and very big pebbles, which probably come from the top of the hill.
8002	layer	sand	pebbles	Compact	Heterogeneous	yellowish	n/a	Archeological layer with flaked stone tools and pebbles. Going towards the bottom, it gradually shows increasing presence of gravel.

Table 8. List of US from Test Pit 8

Material analysis

Lithic analysis (NM, LB, CF, GP, SS, AB, RH)

General characters. At Hayy Al-Sarh raw-material economy for stone production is quite complex, as a broad range of different materials of different provenance are used. The main raw material exploited at the site is radiolarite from near sources located in the ophiolite formation in the Rustaq area. Cherts are all allochthonous. Retouched tools are scarce, with a few scrapers/denticulate tools and a burin.

Radiolarite. The radiolarite at Hayy Al-Sarh is represented by several varieties, primarily:

- R1: Glassy, homogeneous, reddish-brown with greenish veins.
- R2: Medium-grained, opaque, chestnut brown with black veins.
- R3: Glassy, fine-grained, pale brown with abundant slate-gray veins.

Minor varieties include:

- R4: Glassy, fine-grained, very shiny, brown/blue gray with black inclusions.
- R5: Medium/fine-grained, shiny, greenish/gray with black veins.
- R6: Variable grain, light gray to greenish-gray, matte, with dark veining and patinated.
- R7: Medium-grained, non-homogeneous, fawn brown with gray spots, also patinated.

Figure 10 Raw-materials distribution from Hayy Al-Sarh.

Figure 10 Main operational sequence observed at Hayy Al-Sarh, US3003.

The raw materials are primarily in a fresh state, suggesting primary sourcing from tabular formations or rectangular blocks. Two main reduction sequences are observed:

- Unprepared cores: Used to produce flakes and blades via direct percussion, mainly from R2 variety. Large tabular blocks of raw material are flaked with minimal or no preparation, utilizing the natural surfaces to produce quadrangular flakes, elongated flakes, and bladelets. Cores are exploited unidirectionally, often with a circular tendency.
- Bipolar on anvil technique: Employed on small flakes across different radiolarite varieties.

Flint. Flint at the site is found in at least four varieties:

- S1: Fine-grained, non-glassy, dark gray with whitish-beige inclusions.
- S2: Very fine-grained, glassy, translucent, graphite-gray to pearly beige with white inclusions.
- S3: Blond, glassy, ochre-brown to beige with white/orange inclusions.
- S4: Fine-grained, glassy, translucent, gray, beige with reddish bands and black inclusions.

Flint appears to be exotic, with no complete operational sequences identified on site. Only a few cores and a larger blade from S4 are observed, that were probably transported in form of a finished tool/blank.

Quartz and Quartz Crystal. Quartz and quartz crystal are relatively abundant. The operational sequence is complete, starting from secondary deposit-derived small pebbles. Cores are not prepared, with most flakes showing cortical surfaces. Tools include summarily retouched flakes and blades.

Quartzarenite. Quartzarenite, likely sourced near the site, comes in coarse and fine-grained varieties, used to produce regular flakes and laminar flakes from blocks of 5-6 cm. Some summarily retouched tools, such as a scraper, a denticulate tool, and a drill, are noted.

Preliminary conclusions. The lithic assemblage at Hayy Al-Sarh is characterized by a flake-oriented production strategy, reflecting a complex raw-material economy that utilizes a wide range of lithic resources from various sources. The primary material exploited is radiolarite, sourced from nearby ophiolite formations in the Rustaq area. Additionally, a significant portion of the materials, particularly the flints and quartz, appear to be allochthonous, likely procured from the Al Hajar Mountains, in which beige and yellow flints are abundant (Mateiciucová et al. 2023).

The lithic analysis indicates a predominance of flake production, with minimal preparation of cores and a focus on direct percussion techniques. This is especially evident in the exploitation of radiolarite, where large, unprepared tabular blocks were used to produce quadrangular and elongated flakes, as

well as bladelets. The bipolar on anvil technique was also employed, particularly on smaller flakes, across various radiolarite varieties. Despite the variety of materials used, retouched tools are scarce within the assemblage, with only a few scrapers, denticulate tools, and a burin identified. Notably, the assemblage lacks bifacial and trifacial points, which are often associated with Neolithic assemblages. In summary, the lithic assemblage at Hayy Al-Sarh fits well within the broader context of Neolithic flake-oriented industries, with a significant use of both local and non-local materials.

Anthracological analysis (MR)

Present environmental setting. The present vegetation cover in the immediate region around the site is poor. The vegetation on the al-Hajar mountains is characterised by successional stages according to altitude and hydrological conditions. The lower altitudes (300-1100 m a.s.l.) are characterised by open drought deciduous, thorn woodlands of Nubo-Sindian type with *Acacia tortilis*, *Ziziphus spina-christi* and *Rhazya stricta*. From 1100 to 1480m a.s.l. the vegetation is replaced by dwarf shrublands dominated by *Euphorbia larica*, *Pseudogailonia hymenostephana* and *Gailonia aucheri*. At higher elevations (up to 2050 m a.s.l.) the vegetation cover is characterised by evergreen bushlands with *Sideroxylon buxifolium*, *Olea europaea* and *Dodonaea viscosa*. The summit areas (2100-3050 m a.s.l.) harbour cold-deciduous woodlands of Irano-Turanian origin with *Juniperus excelsa* subsp. *polycarpus*, *Lonicera aucheri* and *Cotoneaster nummularia* (Ghazanfar 1991; Patzelt 1996). The Western Hajar is classified as a threatened habitat and a high priority conservation area in the Sultanate of Oman (Ghazanfar 1998).

Materials and methods. The archaeobotanical remains retrieved from the site of Hayy al-Sarh consist of: (a) hand-picked charcoals retrieved from the US 3009 CB01; (b) charcoals, and seeds/fruits collected from the water-flotation processed soil samples retrieved from various contexts. Seventeen soil samples were processed by manual flotation by the members of the excavation team (Table 9). The volume of the samples varied between 1 and 20 liters, with a total volume of processed soil 90 liters of sediment. A 0.1 mm sieves mesh was used during the flotation process. A specific code (Water Flotation Number or WF) was given to each sample.

US	ID	Number of processed samples
3003	SED07	1
3003	SED6	2
3004	SED3	1
3004	SED09	1
3005	SED2	2
3007	SED11	1
3008	SED5	1
3009	SED4	3
3012	SED14	2
3003 sup	SED07	1
3004 Locus 1	SED3	2
Total		17

Table 9. Contexts sampled and treated by water flotation

The observation and taxonomic identification of the charcoal remains were done using a Leica DM LM industrial microscope (magnifications 50x, 100x, 200x, 500x, and 1000x). The observation and taxonomic identification of the seed/fruit remains was done using a Leica M10 stereo zoom microscope (magnifications 8x-80x). Wood anatomical atlases (Fahn *et al.* 1986; Neumann *et al.* 2000) were used as comparative tools for the identification of the anthracological remains.

Results. Bioarchaeological remains were sorted from the float material retrieved during the water flotation (Table 10). Charcoals, seeds, and malacofauna (probably land snails) were retrieved from different samples. The composition of the sediment of the sample WF008 was different, consisting of very fine-grained sand and small pebbles/stones that were not observed in the other samples. In addition, some burnt clay fragments were observed. The question about the age of this sample was raised during the sorting of the bioarchaeological remains and the presence of burnt clay. The sample will be examined further by N. Mazzucco.

The samples WF006 and WF016 did not yield any remains. Most pieces of charcoal were small, no more than 4 mm in length and breadth. A total of 38 charcoals were retrieved from 3 contexts (US3003 SED6, US3009 SED4, and US3012 SED14), and they were all attributed to tamarisk (*Tamarix* sp.; cf. *Tamarix*) (Table 11). In addition, 30 hand-picked charcoals were also identified from the US3009 CB01 and were attributed to tamarisk (19 *Tamarix* sp. remains; 4 cf. *Tamarix* remains), while 7 remains could not be identified beyond the Angiosperm clade (Table 12). From these remains, one charcoal was selected and sent to Groningen for radiocarbon dating.

In total, 291 seed/fruit remains were retrieved from the water-flotation processed samples, from which 152 (52%) consist of Caryophyllaceae (carnation family) seeds, probably modern intrusions (Table 13). In addition, 139 (48%) remains were preserved by bio-mineralisation and were attributed to the borage family (type *Lithospermum*). The presence of mineralised seeds and fruits is common on sites in the Near East and has raised questions about the contemporaneity of these remains to their contexts because whether modern or ancient they have the same aspect (Tengberg *et al.* 2023; Van Zeist and Bakker-Heeres 1982). In addition, the seeds of many plants of the Boraginaceae family are dispersed by ants (Lengyel *et al.* 2010).

WF Number	US	ID	Bioarchaeological remains			Comments
			Charcoals	Seeds	Malacofauna	
WF001	3007	SED11		x		
WF002	3003	SED07		x		
WF003	3003	SED6		xxx		
WF004	3003 sup	SED07		xx	x	
WF005	3012	SED14		x	x	
WF006	3008	SED5				No remains
WF007	3004 Locus 1	SED3		xxx	x	
WF008	3012	SED14	x	x	x	Clay/Argile/Ceramics fragments?
WF009	3004	SED3		xx	x	
WF010	3005	SED2		x	x	
WF011	3009	SED4	xx	x		
WF012	3009	SED4	x		x	
WF013	3005	SED2		x		
WF014	3003	SED6	x	xx	x	
WF015	3009	SED4	x			
WF016	3004	SED09				No remains
WF017	3004 Locus 1	SED3		xx	x	

Table 2. Results of the sorting of the water-flotation processed samples. Symbols: x:0-10 remains; xx: 10-20 remains; xxx: 50< remains.

	WF008	WF011	WF012	WF014	WF015	
US	3012	3009	3009	3003	3009	
ID	SED14	SED4	SED4	SED6	SED4	
Taxonomic identification	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	Total
<i>Tamarix</i> sp.		25	9		1	35
cf. <i>Tamarix</i>	1		1	1		3
Total number of remains	1	25	10	1	1	38

Table 3. Taxonomic identification of anthracological remains (water-flotation).

Taxonomic identification	NR
<i>Tamarix</i> sp.	19
cf. <i>Tamarix</i>	4
Undetermined angiosperm	7
Total	30

Table 4. Taxonomic identification of hand-picked anthracological remains.

			WF001	WF002	WF003	WF004	WF005	WF007	WF008	WF009	WF010	WF011	WF013	WF014	WF017	
			24-Jan	24-Jan	23-Jan	24-Jan	25-Jan		25-Jan	24-Jan	22-Jan	23-Jan	22-Jan	23-Jan		
			3007	3003	3003	3003	3012	004 Locus	3012	3004	3005	3009	3005	3003	004 Locus 1	
			SED11	SED07	SED6	SED07 sup.	SED12	SED3	SED14	SED3	SED2	SED4	SED2	SED6	SED3	
Taxonomic identification	Mode of preservation	Type of remain	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	NR	Total
Boraginaceae type <i>Lithospermum</i>	Mineralised	Achene	3	3	7	31		8	1	46	3	4		9	24	139
Caryophyllaceae	Modern intrusions	Urticle			51		1	97					1	1	1	152
Total Number of remains			3	3	58	31	1	105	1	46	3	4	1	10	25	291

Table 5. Taxonomic identification of seed/fruit remains (water-flotation)

Discussion. The taxonomic identification of tamarisk charcoal remains is not possible beyond the genus level. Five tamarisk species are attested in the flora of Oman:

- Tamarix aphylla*: is attested throughout Oman, in sandy areas, wadi beds and by water courses, 50-350 m,
- T. stricta*: is attested in northern Oman, in the foothills of the mountains, in dry and stony wadi beds and sandy depressions, 50-100 m,
- T. mascatensis*: is attested throughout Oman, grows in sandy and saline soils, in wadi beds, 50-300 m,
- T. arabica*: is attested throughout Oman. Common in dry wadi beds and on disturbed poorly drained soils, 60-350 m,
- T. aucheriana*: is attested in northern and central Oman, common in saline depressions at sea level and on sandy soils, and at the edges of sea inlets and littoral swamps, 10-50 m.

Based on phytogeographical grounds, the tamarisk species *Tamarix stricta* and *T. aucheriana* can be excluded. The presence of *Tamarix* in the assemblages of Hayy al-Sarh could be related to the presence wadi beds near the site. Due to the very small number of charcoal remains as well as the restricted number of contexts, it is not possible to draw any conclusions about the palaeoenvironment around the site. However, the occurrence of tamarisk in all studied contexts may indicate the importance of this feature in the vegetation cover. The tamarisk (*Tamarix aphylla*) exudes salt through glands situated on its minute leaves that were traditionally used for cooking. It also produces small amounts of edible, dark-coloured resin (Tengberg 2008).

The archaeobotanical remains retrieved from Hayy al-Sarh add to the available dataset about the vegetation cover and exploitation of plant resources during the Neolithic at sites in the interior of the Oman peninsula. The available dataset for the neolithic sites in the interior of the Oman peninsula remains very restricted compared to the available dataset for the coastal sites that show the exploitation of mangrove formations – *Avicennia marina* in particular – for firewood (Berger *et al.* 2013; Biagi 1999; Biagi & Nisbet 1992, 2006; Tengberg 2005). The analysis of charcoal remains from the site al-Buhais 18 (5100-4300 cal BCE) (Uerpmann *et al.* 2000) shows the exploitation of open thorn woodlands dominated by *Acacia* spp. and *Ziziphus spina-christi*, with an overwhelming preference for *Acacia tortilis*. The predominance of this species in the assemblage appears linked to the composition of the vegetation cover around the site, as well as its use as leaf fodder and secondarily as a source of firewood (Tengberg 2008).

Conclusions and suggestions for future work. The anthracological results obtained from the 2024 campaign, although monotonous in terms of the richness of the taxonomic spectrum (presence of tamarisk), are rather encouraging for future work at the site. They also add to the limited available inland records in Neolithic southeast Arabia (Bretzke *et al.* 2018). Despite the small number of anthracological

remains, it is suggested that systematic sampling be continued during future excavation seasons. According to previous tests conducted at other archaeological sites, the dry sieving method seems to be appropriate for the extraction of archaeobotanical remains in desertic environments (Milon 2023). It is therefore suggested that the method of dry sieving be tested at the site to examine whether the extraction method affects the preservation of charred remains.

Pollen analysis (DA)

Preliminary data. Pollen analysis of a series of samples taken from the section east of Area A2 (Figure 6) is still ongoing. Nevertheless, we have some very preliminary results that can be shared. Despite the low pollen concentration within the samples, partly due to the insufficient amount of sediment analyzed, the presence of some relevant pollen and non-pollen palynomorphs provides interesting insights into the environmental setting. There is evidence suggesting past wet conditions. Among the arboreal species identified, temperate species like oak were found, along with pollen from alder, which typically indicates the proximity of water bodies or riparian environments. This interpretation is further supported by the discovery of *Pseudoschizaeae*, an algal cyst indicative of seasonal wet/dry cycles (Scott 1992; Arobba et al. 2018), and *testate amoebae*, organisms that inhabit shallow water pools (Charman 2001). These findings suggest a more complex and varied environmental history than previously understood. However, these preliminary results need to be confirmed through more extensive sampling and analysis during the next campaign to ensure the reliability of the data and to gain a more comprehensive understanding of the site's environmental conditions.

Malacological remains and other ornaments (KL, NM)

Figure 6 Shells, shell beads and other ornaments recovered from the site.

Preliminary data. A small assemblage of shells, shell beads and other ornaments (a fragment of a coral and an unfinished stone pendant on a calcareous rock) is in course of being studied. Several shell beads from *Polinices mammalia*, a typical ornament for Omani Neolithic sites, have been found.

Conclusions

The 2024 excavation campaign at Hayy Al-Sarh has yielded significant insights into the site's archaeological and environmental context, contributing to our broader understanding of Neolithic settlement patterns in the interior of Oman. The excavation of a stratified Neolithic layer in extension is per se a highly relevant goal for this season.

The discovery of LOCUS2, a complex structure potentially representing a circular dwelling, is a major highlight of this campaign. The structure's arched outline, with associated postholes, and stone accumulation indicate a specific organization of the space to host a temporal shelter. The partial excavation of LOCUS2 has already revealed a significant quantity of lithic remains and other artifacts, with further excavation planned for the next season to fully uncover and understand this feature.

Preliminary pollen and anthracological analyses have begun to reveal the environmental conditions surrounding the site during the Neolithic period. Evidence of taxa associated with wet conditions, such as alder and temperate species like oak, coupled with the presence of specific non-pollen palynomorphs, suggests that the area may have experienced periodic wet/dry cycles. This finding, alongside the identification of tamarisk in the charcoal samples, provides a glimpse into a more varied and potentially wetter past environment, contrasting with the arid conditions observed today.

The lithic industry with allochthonous materials, and the presence of marine shells remains indicate that the site was rooted and connected to broader regional networks. The evidence of allochthonous materials highlights Hayy Al-Sarh's role in facilitating interactions between coastal and inland communities, opening perspective on the possibility of reconstructing mobility patterns of Neolithic populations, as initially postulated at the beginning of this project.

The detailed study of campsites in the foothill and mountainous areas of the Al-Hajar mountains will improve our understanding of Omani Neolithic, their territorial organization, and the relationship between coastal and inland resource

The 2024 campaign has laid a solid foundation for future research. The planned excavation of the remaining half of LOCUS2 will be crucial in fully interpreting this structure. Additionally, further pollen analysis and more extensive sampling during the next campaign will be essential to confirm the preliminary environmental findings and refine our understanding of the site's ecological history. In conclusion, the 2024 season at Hayy Al-Sarh has provided important data that will not only enhance our knowledge of the site's occupation and usage but also contribute to broader discussions about Neolithic lifeways in the Arabian Peninsula. The ongoing research at Hayy Al-Sarh promises to yield further significant discoveries, particularly in terms of how this site fits into the wider landscape of prehistoric Oman.

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